

IKKINCHI TARTIBLI CHIZIQLI DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMANI YECHIMINI GILBERT FAZOSIDA QURISH

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H Gilbert fazosi va $u, f \in H$ bo'lsin. Ushbu tenglamani qaraylik

$$Au(x) = f(x) \quad (1)$$

bu yerda $u(x)$ –noma'lum funksiya, $A: H \rightarrow H$ o'zi o'ziga qo'shma operator bo'lib, $\forall x \in H$ uchun quyidagi shart bajariladi:

$$A(x, x) \geq m(x, x), \quad m > 0. \quad (2)$$

$H_A \subseteq H$ - gilbert fazosining qism fazosi bo'lsin. Bu fazoda skalyar ko'paytmani quyidagicha aniqlaymiz : $(u, v)_A = (Au, v)$. H Gilbert fazosi va unda aniqlangan g_1, g_2, \dots, g_n chiziqli erkli elementlar va $H_n = L\{g_1, g_2, \dots, g_n\}$ - chiziqli qobiq ularning ustiga qurilgan bo'lsin. Agar $u_n \in H_n$ uchun

$$u_n = \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_k g_k$$

bo'lsa, u holda (1) tenglama quyidagi ko'rinishni oladi

$$Au = \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_k Ag_k = f$$

g_n - sistema chiziqli erkli bo'lgani uchun (1) tenglamaning har ikkala tomonini g_m ga ko'paytirib ushbu

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_k (Ag_k, g_m) = (g_m, f) \quad (3)$$

ifodaga ega bo'lamiz. Bu tenglamalar sistemasidan α_k larni topsak,

$$u = \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_k^{(n)} g_k$$

noma'lum funksiyani topgan bo'lamiz

Quyidagi differensial tenglamani qaraymiz,

$$-\frac{d}{dx} \left[p(x) \frac{dx}{dx} \right] + q(x)u(x) = f(x), \quad 0 < x < 1 \quad (5)$$

Chegaraviy sharti

$$u(0) = u(1) = 0,$$

bundan tashqari

$$p(x) \geq c_0 > 0 \quad (6)$$

Mos operatorni A bilan belgilaymiz. Agar $D(A) = \{W_2^2[0,1]; u(0) = u(1) = 0\}$

bo'lsa, u holda A operator o'z-o'ziga qo'shma operator bo'ladi.

Bu yerda $H_A = W_2^1[0,1]$ va skalyar ko'paytma quyidagi ko'rinishida ifodalanadi

$$(u, v)_A = \int_0^1 [p(x)u'(x)v'(x) + q(x)u(x)v(x)] dx \quad (7)$$

H_A fazoda ixtiyoriy n uchun H_n^* qismfazoni qaraymiz, bu fazoda quyidagi funksiyalar ketma-ketligini quramiz

$$\phi_k(x) = \theta(nx - k), \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1, \quad k = 1, \dots, n - 1,$$

bu yerda $\theta(t) = \max\{0, 1 - |t|\}$. Bu funksiyalar ketma-ketligining umumiy ifodalanishi quyidagicha bo'ladi:

$$\phi_k(x) = \begin{cases} 0, & 0 \leq x \leq (k-1)/n \\ nx - (k-1), & (k-1)/n \leq x \leq k/n \\ (k+1) - nx, & k/n \leq x \leq (k+1)/n \\ 0, & (k+1)/n \leq x \leq 1 \end{cases}$$

Bu funksiya grafigi har bir $\phi_k(x)$ – funksiya uchun k ning qiymatlariga bog'liq holda chiziladi.

H_n^* fazo elementlarini quyidagicha aniqlash mumkin:

$$u_n = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \alpha_k \phi_k(x), \quad x \in [0,1] \quad (8)$$

(8) ni (5) tenglamaga qo'yib, quyidagi tengliklarni olamiz

$$\begin{aligned} & -h^{-1}[\alpha_{k-1}p_k - \alpha_k(p_k + p_{k+1}) + \alpha_{k+1}(p_{k+1})] + \\ & + h[\alpha_{k-1}q_{k-1,k} + \alpha_k q_{kk} + \alpha_{k+1}q_{k+1,k}] = hf_k, \\ & k = 1, 2, \dots, n - 1. \end{aligned}$$

Olingan natijani quyidagicha yozishimiz mumkin

$$\begin{aligned} & -\frac{1}{h}(p_{k+1} \frac{\alpha_{k+1} - \alpha_k}{h} - p_k \frac{\alpha_k - \alpha_{k-1}}{h}) + \\ & + \alpha_{k-1}q_{k-1,k} + \alpha_k q_{kk} + \alpha_{k+1}q_{k+1,k} = f_k. \end{aligned}$$

Bu yerda quyidagi belgilashlardan foydalandik

$$p_k = h^{-1} \int_{kh-h}^{kh} p(x) dx, \quad k = 1, \dots, n \quad q_{km} = h^{-1} \int_0^1 q(x) \phi_k(x) \phi_m(x) dx,$$

$$f_k = h^{-1} \int_0^1 f(x) \phi_k(x) dx,$$

U holda

$$(\phi_k, \phi_k)_A = h^{-1}(p_k + p_{k+1}), \quad (\phi_{k-1}, \phi_k)_A = -h^{-1}p_k,$$

$$(\phi_{k+1}, \phi_k)_A = -h^{-1}p_{k+1}$$

Bulardan quyidagi ifodani hosil qilamiz

$$\alpha_{k-1}(hq_{k-1,k} - h^{-1}p_k) + \alpha_k(hq_{k,k} + h^{-1}(p_k + p_{k+1})) + \alpha_{k+1}(hq_{k+1,k} - h^{-1}p_{k+1}) = hf_k$$

$$k = 1, 2, \dots, n-1, \quad \alpha_0 = \alpha_n = 0$$

Biz bu ifodani har bir k uchun yozib chiqsak α_k lar noma'lum bo'lgan tenglamalar sistemasiga keladi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Sh. Alimov ma'ruzalari, Rits usuli
2. С. Михлин “Вариационные методы в математической физике” Москв-1970.
3. Б а р и Н. К. “Теория линейных операторов”, «Наука», 1966.